

Distance Measurements Method for The Demite Pronunciation Assessment

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Abstract— The Demite is an educational game with a horror genre using Augmented Reality technology and Speech Recognition. In this game, the player will capture and eliminate ghosts with English pronunciation. Therefore, players will not only catch and eliminate ghosts, but players will also train their English pronunciation correctly. To find out the exact and correct pronunciation in English, The Demite requires an assessment system to measure the distance in the pronunciation of English words. The assessment system requires a method to measure the distance parameters that will be used in the assessment system. Parameters to be measured are Phonetic, Syllable, and Phonetic Length. In this study focused on choosing the right method between Levenshtein Distance, Euclidian Distance, and Manhattan Distance in measuring the distance of these parameters. Based on the results of the tests performed, it was concluded that it is possible to use Levenshtein distance in measuring the distance between phonetic and after observing the test data in syllable and phonetic length measurements, the Manhattan distance method is more appropriate to measure syllable and phonetic length distances even if viewed the average measurement of the Manhattan distance and Euclidean distance is almost the same value. However, when the distance from syllable and phonetic length is far, Euclidean measurements take the midpoint of the accumulation of all parameters, whereas, The Demite assessment system requires the sum of all distances obtained from these parameters. Therefore, the Manhattan distance method is used which measures the distance of the Syllable and Phonetic parameter by sum all the distance values obtained.

Keywords— *Distance Measurements, Levenshtein Distance, Euclidean Distance, Manhattan Distance.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Based on the results of a survey in 2017 from Education First (EF), in the English-speaking ability, Indonesia was ranked 10

out of 20 countries in Asia with EF English Proficiency Index (EPI) score 52,15 and was categorized low skilled. For Indonesians themselves, they often make mistakes in English pronunciation because there are words in English has many similarities in pronunciation but have different meanings. therefore, an educational game The Demite was created which was expected to improve English pronunciation, especially for Indonesians.

The Demite is horror genre education mobile game using Augmented Reality and Speech Recognition technology. By using Augmented Reality (AR) technology, players are expected the playing experience feels more real. In this game, the appearance of ghosts is based on geographical applied to Augmented Reality. To be able to accept the player's speech and translate it into text in The Demite, the Speech-To-Text application is used as speech recognition technology. Therefore, the existence of this technology is expected to make the learning experience in English pronunciation more interesting.

in this game, the player will capture and eliminate ghosts like a paranormal. however, to capture or eliminate the ghost, the player must say words that can weaken the ghost. The words that can weaken the ghost will be spoken using English. Therefore, players will not only catch and eliminate ghosts, but players will learn to pronounce the words in English correctly. To find out the exact and correct words spoken by players, The Demite Game requires an assessment system to measure the pronunciation of English words with parameters that are adjusted for Indonesians. The parameters that will be used in the game are Phonetic, syllable, Phonetic Length, and word level [1]. For syllable and phonetic length parameters no more than 25% in pronunciation assessment. The results of the calculation of the assessment will be accumulated into damage against ghosts. This damage will make ghosts weak.

In measuring the pronunciation of words, the data to be used is obtained from available data sources. To measure the pronunciation that will be used in the assessment system for The Demite, will use the similarity distance measurement method. The similarity distance measurements are Levenshtein Distance, Manhattan Distance, and Euclidean Distance will use. Therefore, we are interested in investigating Levenshtein Distance, Manhattan Distance, Euclidean Distance to measure the pronunciation of English words in The Demite.

II. DISTANCE MEASUREMENTS

A. Levenshtein Distance

Levenshtein Distance is an algorithm used to measure distances between two strings [2][3][4]. To measure the distance similarity using the minimum-edit-distance operation is Insertion, deletion, and substitution [2][3][4]. Each operation used has a weight value of 1 [3]. In the case of The Demite game, the first string is phonetic from input and the second string is phonetic data from the dataset. English phonetic is used based on the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) standard. The results of calculating the distance between phonetics using Levenshtein Distance will be used in the assessment system in The Demite game.

In the case of calculating the phonetic distance between waist and wine, the distance value is 3. Waist has phonetic "weist" and wine has phonetic "wain". The operation process to calculate the distance between "weist" and "wain" is as follows:

1. First operation, substitution "e" with "a" (weist → waist);
2. Second operation, substitution "s" with "n" (waist → waint);
3. Third Operation, Deletion "t" (waint → wais).

With the cost of each operating weight is 1, then the distance between phonetic waist and phonetic wine is 3. To see the matrix value representation of the distance measurement can be seen in the following table

Table 1 Levenshtein Distance Example

		w	a	i	n
	0	1	2	3	4
w	1	0	1	2	3
e	2	1	1	2	3
i	3	2	2	1	2
s	4	3	3	2	2
t	5	4	4	3	3

The last value in the lower right corner is a value that states the distance from the measurement of the distance between the phonetic waist and the phonetic wine that is 3.

B. Manhattan Distance

it is also called L1 distance or city block [5][6], originally proposed by Minkowsky which is defined by [6]

$$D_{Manhattan}(x_i, x_j) = \sum_{k=1}^d |x_{ik} - x_{jk}|$$

This measurement measures the distance from x_i to x_j by sum all the closest distances from the point between x_i to x_j [6][7].

Figure 1 Manhattan Distance Representation

C. Euclidean Distance

it also called L2 distance, this distance measurement is also included in the matrix distance [5][6]. Euclidean Distance is defined with

$$D_{Euclidean}(x_i, x_j) = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^d (x_{ik} - x_{jk})^2}$$

Euclidean distance is the shortest path to x_j between x_i

which is a straight line as shown in Figure 2 [6][7]

Figure 2 Euclidean Distance Representation

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

Design of an assessment system that is used to carry out the process of catching ghosts in The Demite game. Flowchart

design from the pronunciation assessment process for ghost capture is as follows.

Figure 3 The Demite Pronunciation Assessment Flowchart

The following stages will be used in the pronunciation assessment process for ghost capture in The Demite.

1. Firstly, the system will start the ghost capture process. The process will display the word that must be said for the player, namely Keyword.
2. Second, after showing the Keyword the process of calling parameter data is Phonetic, Syllable, Phonetic Length and Word Level based on the keyword that appears.
3. Third, the system starts the process of listening to the player's voice.

4. Fourth, the player will start saying the word, then Speech to text will start the voice recognition process based on player input. The input speech results from the player that have been processed with Speech-To-Text are text words with string data types.
5. Fifth, the process will take parameters from datamuse based on the text generated from STT, the phonetic type is data string. Syllable and Phonetic Length which are integer data types.
6. Sixth, the results of phonetic retrieval of the words spoken by the player will be measured the distance of phonetic similarity generated by keywords using the Similarity Distance method. To measure phonetic parameters that have string data types, the levenshtein distance method is used. to measure syllable and phonetic length parameters that are integer data types using Manhattan / Euclidean Distance. The output of the distance measurement process is the distance value between the Parameters.
7. Seventh, the results of the similarity distance measurement process will be processed to determine damage against ghosts. The damage process is a process of accumulation between similarity value and Word Level. The harder or higher the level, the more damages will be received by ghosts. Word level is obtained from the output word level keyword.
8. eight, the condition if damage to the ghost makes the health point run out then the ghost capture process. If not, the process is repeated to the first process until the ghost health point runs out.

In the pronunciation assessment process, it will get a similarity value based on the distance calculation from Phonetic, Syllable, and Phonetic Length parameters.

Figure 4 Distance from parameter example

The distance calculation results from Syllable and phonetic length will only have an impact of 25% from the Phonetic distance calculation result. Similarity values are defined by

$$Sim_{value} = Sim_{Phonetic} - (Sim_{Parameter} \cdot 0,25 Sim_{Phonetic})$$

- Sim_{value} = Similarity Value
- $Sim_{Phonetic}$ = Similarity phonetic (Levenshtein)
- $Sim_{Parameter}$ = Similarity syllable dan Phonetic Length (Euclidean/Manhattan)

9		hot	hot	0	0
10		give	give	0	0
11	Give	give	give	0	0
12		give	give	0	0
13	Trap	trap	trap	0	0
14		trap	trap	0	0
15		trap	trap	0	0

IV. TESTING

Testing the word pronunciation distance measurement on The Demite using Levenshtein Distance, Manhattan Distance, and Euclidean Distance with 40 test words. Each word is tested with different, similar and same words.

A. Testing with The Same Words

In testing with the same word, the Levenshtein Distance measurement method will measure the distance between phonetic from keywords and phonetic from speech input. Euclidean and Manhattan distance measurement methods will measure the distance between syllables and phonetic lengths of keywords with syllables and phonetic lengths of speech input. After all parameter data is measured, will be tested to see the similarity value.

In testing distance measurement of Phonetic with the same word using Levenstein Distance, the word to be tested is 40 words and tested with three times experiments. The following sample data table represents 40 test data.

Table 2 Phonetic Distance using Levenshtein with The Same Word Sample

No	Keyword	Speak k This	STT Spoken	Score	
				Distance	Similarity
1	Try	try	try	0	100%
2		try	try	0	100%
3		try	try	0	100%
4	Wet	wet	wet	0	100%
5		wet	wet	0	100%
6		wet	wet	0	100%
7	Hot	hot	hot	0	100%
8		hot	hot	0	100%
9		hot	hot	0	100%
10	Give	give	give	0	100%
11		give	give	0	100%
12		give	give	0	100%
13	Trap	trap	trap	0	100%
14		trap	trap	0	100%
15		trap	trap	0	100%

According to the test results with the same word, the average distance values of the 40 data test were obtained and tested in three times experiments for each data which was 0 with an average similarity 100%.

Testing in distance measurement of syllable and phonetic length with the same word using Euclidean and Manhattan distance. in this test will be compared the measurement value of Euclidean and Manhattan distance. The following sample data table represents 40 test data.

No	Keyword	Spea k This	STT Spoken	Distance	
				Manhattan	Euclidean
1	Try	try	try	0	0
2		try	try	0	0
3		try	try	0	0
4	Wet	wet	wet	0	0
5		wet	wet	0	0
6		wet	wet	0	0
7	Hot	hot	hot	0	0
8		hot	hot	0	0

Table 3 Syllable and Phonetic Length distance using Euclidean and Manhattan with The Same Word Sample

Based on the results of testing the syllable and phonetic length distances from the same word, the Euclidean and Manhattan distance calculations show the same value of 0, which means that it has no distance.

Next, a test was conducted to see the similarity value of the accumulated results of all phonetic distance calculations using levenshtein distance, syllable and phonetic length calculations using Euclidean and Manhattan distance calculations. The purpose of the test is to see and compare the similarity value between the Euclidean method and Manhattan distance when tested with the same word. The following is a sample table similarity value by testing 40 words.

Table 4 Euclidean and Manhattan similarity value with The Same Word Sample

No	Keyword	Speak This	STT Spoken	Similarity Value	
				Manhattan	Euclidean
1	Try	try	try	100%	100%
2		try	try	100%	100%
3		try	try	100%	100%
4	Wet	wet	wet	100%	100%
5		wet	wet	100%	100%
6		wet	wet	100%	100%
7	Hot	hot	hot	100%	100%
8		hot	hot	100%	100%
9		hot	hot	100%	100%
10	Give	give	give	100%	100%
11		give	give	100%	100%
12		give	give	100%	100%
13	Trap	trap	trap	100%	100%
14		trap	trap	100%	100%
15		trap	trap	100%	100%

Based on the results of the test with the same word, shows that both Manhattan and Euclidean distance methods have the same value with an average 100% similarity value.

B. Testing with Different Words

In testing with different words, the Levenshtein Distance measurement method will measure the distance between phonetic from keywords and phonetic from speech input. Euclidean and Manhattan distance measurement methods will measure the distance between syllables and phonetic lengths of keywords with syllables and phonetic lengths of speech input. After all parameter data is measured, then testing will be performed to see the similarity values when tested with different words

measurement with different words using Levenstein Distance, the word to be tested amounted to 40 words and tested with 3 times experiments. The following data sample table represents 40 test data.

No	Keyword	Speak This	STT Spoken	Similarity Value	
				Manhattan	Euclidean
1	Try	open	open	0%	0%
2		work	work	19,17%	19,17%
3		join	join	32,79%	32,79%
4	Wet	cheerful	cheerful	11,38%	11,66%
5		dry	dry	19,17%	19,17%
6		blow	blow	19,17%	19,17%
7	Hot	swim	swim	19,17%	19,17%
8		sound	sound	15,79%	15,79%
9		smile	smile	15,79%	15,79%
10	Give	easy	easy	0%	0%
11		sad	sad	25%	25%
12		park	park	19,17%	19,17%
13	Trap	office	office	0%	0%
14		long	long	19,17%	19,17%
15		decide	decide	13,75%	14,07%

No	Keyword	Speak This	STT Spoken	Score	
				Distance	Similarity
1	Try	open	open	6	0%
2		work	work	4	20%
3		join	join	4	34%
4	Wet	cheerful	cheerful	7	13%
5		dry	dry	4	20%
6		blow	blow	4	20%
7	Hot	swim	swim	4	20%
8		sound	sound	5	17%
9		smile	smile	5	17%
10	Give	easy	easy	4	0%
11		sad	sad	3	25%
12		park	park	4	20%
13	Trap	office	office	5	0%
14		long	long	4	20%
15		decide	decide	6	15%

Table 5 Phonetic Distance using Levenshtein with The Different Word Sample

According to the results of testing with different words, the average similarity values of the 40 data test were obtained and three times tested experiments with different word for each of the data is 16%.

Testing in distance measurement of syllable and phonetic length with the different word using Euclidean and Manhattan distance. in this test will be compared the measurement value of Euclidean and Manhattan distance. The following sample data table represents 40 test data.

Table 6 Syllable and Phonetic Length distance using Euclidean and Manhattan with The Different Word Sample

No	Keyword	Speak This	STT Spoken	Distance	
				Manhattan	Euclidean
1	Try	open	open	2	1,41
2		work	work	1	1,00
3		join	join	1	1,00
4		cheerful	cheerful	4	3,16

The average similarity value of the 40 data tests was obtained and three times tested by different word experiments. For Manhattan Distance average is 15% with the highest distance 33% and the lowest distance 0%. For Euclidean Distance average is 15% with the highest distance 32,79% and the lowest distance 0%.

5	Wet	dry	dry	0	0,00
6		blow	blow	0	0,00
7		swim	swim	1	1,00
8	Hot	sound	sound	4	3,16
9		smile	smile	2	2,00
10	Give	easy	easy	1	1,00
11		sad	sad	0	0,00
12		park	park	1	1,00
13	Trap	office	office	1	1,00
14		long	long	1	1,00
15		decide	decide	3	2,48

According to the results of testing with different words, the average Distance values of the 40 data test were obtained and

three times tested experiments with different word. For Manhattan Distance average was 1,46 with the highest distance 4 and the lowest distance 0. For Euclidean Distance average was 1,28 with the highest distance 3,16 and the lowest distance 0.

C. Testing with Similar Words

In testing with the similar word, the Levenshtein Distance measurement method will measure the distance between phonetic from keywords and phonetic from speech input. Euclidean and Manhattan distance measurement methods will measure the distance between syllables and phonetic lengths of keywords with syllables and phonetic lengths of speech input. After all parameter data has been measured, testing will be performed to see the similarity value when tested with the same word.

measurement with similar words using Levenshtein Distance, the word to be tested amounted to 40 words and tested with 3 times experiments. The following data sample table represents 40 test data.

No	Keyword	Spoken This	STT Spoken	Score	
				Distance	Similarity
1	Try	cry	cry	1	80%
2		tray	tray	1	80%
3		troy	troy	1	80%
4	Wet	what	what	1	75%
5		where	where	1	75%
6		web	web	1	75%
7	Hot	hat	hat	1	75%
8		hit	hit	1	75%
9		bought	bought	1	75%
10	Give	gave	gave	1	80%
11		gyve	gyve	1	80%
12		gift	gift	2	60%
13	Trap	trip	trip	1	80%
14		strap	strap	1	84%
15		crap	crap	1	80%

The next test is testing each parameter to see the similarity value. The following is the test sample data to look for similarity values by testing different words.

Table 7 Euclidean and Manhattan similarity value with The Different Word Sample

Table 8 Phonetic Distance using Levenshtein with The Similar Word Sample

According to the test results with the similar word, the average similarity values of the 40 data test were obtained and tested in three times experiments for each data which was 77%.

The following is a test of the same word distance measurement with the syllable and phonetic length parameters using Manhattan distance and Euclidean Distance.

Table 9 Syllable and Phonetic Length distance using Euclidean and Manhattan with The Similar Word Sample

No	Keyword	Speak This	STT Spoken	Distance	
				Manhattan	Euclidean
1	Try	cry	cry	0	0,00
2		tray	tray	0	0,00
3		troy	troy	0	0,00
4	Wet	what	what	0	0,00
5		where	where	0	0,00
6		web	web	0	0,00
7	Hot	hat	hat	0	0,00
8		hit	hit	0	0,00
9		bought	bought	0	0,00
10	Give	gave	gave	1	1,00
11		gyve	gyve	1	1,00
12		gift	gift	1	1,00
13	Trap	trip	trip	0	0,00
14		strap	strap	0	0,00
15		crap	crap	0	0,00

According to the test results with the similar word, the average distance value for Manhattan was 0,26 with the highest distance 1 and the lowest distance 0. For Euclidean distance was 1 with the highest distance 1 and the lowest distance 0.

The testing is test to see the similarity values of the results of the distance calculation for each parameter. The following is the test sample data to find the similarity value by the similar word.

Table 10 Euclidean and Manhattan similarity value with The Similar Word Sample

No	Keyword	Speak This	STT Spoken	Distance	
				Manhattan	Euclidean
1	Try	cry	cry	80%	80%
2		tray	tray	80%	80%
3		troy	troy	80%	80%
4	Wet	what	what	75%	75%
5		where	where	75%	75%
6		web	web	75%	75%
7	Hot	hat	hat	75%	75%
8		hit	hit	75%	75%
9		bought	bought	75%	75%
10	Give	gave	gave	76,67%	76,67%
11		gyve	gyve	76,67%	76,67%
12		gift	gift	57,50%	57,50%
13	Trap	trip	trip	80%	80%
14		strap	strap	81%	81%
15		crap	crap	80%	80%

The average similarity values for Manhattan distance were 76% with the highest 81% and the lowest 58%. for Euclidean distance was 76% with the highest 81% and the lowest 58%.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the tests performed, it was concluded that it is possible to use Levenshtein distance in measuring the distance between phonetic and after observing the test data in syllable and phonetic length measurements, the Manhattan

distance method is more appropriate to measure syllable and phonetic length distances even if viewed the average measurement of the Manhattan distance and Euclidean distance is almost the same value. However, when the distance from syllable and phonetic length is far, Euclidean measurements take the midpoint of the accumulation of all parameters, whereas, The Demite assessment system requires the sum of all distances obtained from these parameters. Therefore, the Manhattan distance method is used which measures the distance of the Syllable and Phonetic parameter by sum all the distance values obtained.

REFERENCES

- [1] Isaacs, Talia, and Pavel Trofimovich. Second language pronunciation assessment: Interdisciplinary perspectives. Multilingual Matters, 2017.
- [2] Ziólko, Bartosz, Jakub Galka, and Dawid Skurzok. "Speech modelling using phoneme segmentation and modified weighted Levenshtein distance." Audio Language and Image Processing (ICALIP), 2010 International Conference on. IEEE, 2010.
- [3] Droppo, Jasha, and Alex Acero. "Context dependent phonetic string edit distance for automatic speech recognition." Acoustics Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP), 2010 IEEE International Conference on. IEEE, 2010.
- [4] Istepanean R., Laxminarayan S., Pattichis C. S., *M-Health Emerging Mobile Health Systems*, Springer Science, 2006.
- [5] Zezula, Pavel, et al. Similarity search: the metric space approach. Vol. 32. Springer Science & Business Media, 2006.
- [6] Hertz, Tomer. Learning Distance Functions: Algo Rithms and Applications. Hebrew University, 2006.
- [7] Ranjitkar, Hari Sagar, and Sudip Karki. "Comparison of A*, Euclidean and Manhattan distance using Influence map in MS. Pac-Man." (2016).
- [8] Isaacs, Talia, and Luke Harding. "Pronunciation assessment." Language Teaching 50.3, 2017.
- [9] Isaacs, Talia, et al. "Fully automated speaking assessment: Changes to proficiency testing and the role of pronunciation." The Routledge handbook of English pronunciation, 2018.
- [10] Landers, R. N. "An introduction to game-based assessment: Frameworks for the measurement of knowledge, skills, abilities and other human characteristics using behaviors observed within videogames". International Journal of Gaming and Computer-Mediation Simulations, 2015.